

IMPACT OF HUMOR STYLES AND MINDFULNESS ON QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE. MEDIATING ROLE OF RELATIONSHIP SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are world's most common reason of death and are responsible for quality of life (QOL) impairment. The current research was carried out to study the impact of humor styles and mindfulness on quality of life among cardiovascular disease patients. The mediating role of relationship satisfaction was also being studied. Sample of 160 patients were recruited (83 males and 77 females) with an age range of 35 to 65 will be taken from Armed Force Institute of Cardiology (AFIC) Rawalpindi. The study was quantitative in nature. Humor and Mindfulness was measured using Humor Styles Questionnaire (Martin, 2003) and Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale (Brown & Ryan 2003) respectively. Quality of Life and Relationship Satisfaction was measured using The World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire (WHOQOL Group, 1997) and Couples Satisfaction Index (Funk & Rogge, 2007) respectively. The data was analyzed using SPSS and Process macro. Results showed significant positive relationship between humor styles, mindfulness and quality of life among patients with cardiovascular diseases. Relationship satisfaction emerges as significant mediator on relationship between humor, mindfulness and quality of life among cardiovascular diseases patients. The study will contribute to the existing literature and will be helpful to create awareness among people about humor and mindfulness as coping techniques. Humor, mindfulness and relationship satisfaction may enhance the positive psychological functioning and restructure CVD patient's negative attitudes and behaviors related to health.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are cardiac and blood vessel disorders which involves coronary heart disease, stroke, rheumatic heart disease and other conditions (Mendis et al., 2011). The World Health Organization (2017) had reported that, globally, cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains the

leading cause of mortality and takes the lives of over 17 million individuals every year. This will be the leading cause of mortality in 2030 according to global health estimates (World Health Organization, 2018). Cardiovascular diseases are main health issue in Pakistan, and patient numbers are increasing day by day.

Humor has been a useful coping mechanism for several long-term life incidents. Humorous communication among patients and associates is a valuable tool for people to control, cope with and recover from traumatic experiences. Research indicates that humor provides numerous health benefits, which can generally be grouped into three closely interconnected categories: physiological (Martin, 2001), psychological (School & Ragan, 2003), and social factors (Alberts, 1990; Wuerffel, 1986). Humor is considered as one of the 24 strengths of character, moral and generally recognized traits identified by positive psychology which leads to a good life when used in conjunction with practical wisdom (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). Humor is one of the strengths of character that closely associate with life satisfaction and is considered as important factor like intelligence, bravery, and affection (Proyer & Buschor, 2013).

Researchers viewed humor as having a unique and optimistic unitary nature (Cann et al., 2010). Martin et al., (2003) have outlined four kinds of humor. Affiliative and self-enhancing, are optimistic and helpful to oneself and others while aggressive and self-defeating, are damaging and harmful to both the individual and others. Exploratory factor analyses suggest that these four humor styles are largely independent, as indicated by relatively weak correlations among the scales (Martin, 2003). While individuals may demonstrate aspects of each style to varying degrees, one humor style typically emerges as their dominant or characteristic approach. Of these, affiliative and self-enhancing humor are viewed as positive as they foster coping and strengthen social connections, whereas aggressive and self-defeating humor are regarded as negative, given their potential to harm oneself or others (Martin et al., 2003).

Individuals initiating humorous dialog exhibit numerous physiological benefits to health. Another notable benefit of humor is its positive impact on immune system functioning. According to Bennett and Lengacher (2009), the stress-relieving effects of humor contribute to immunoenhancement. Specifically, engaging with or being exposed to humor can boost immune

activity by increasing the natural killer (NK) cells, which play a vital role in destroying carcinomas, sarcomas, melanomas, leukemia cells, and various viral illness (Bennett & Lengacher, 2009). These findings indicate that as cardiovascular patients experience improved quality of life, humor may strengthen their resistance to infections by supporting immune system activity. Considering that procedures such as bypass surgeries, stents, and angiograms often carry infection risks, the immunological benefits of humor can play a significant role in enhancing physical recovery and overall health.

The relation among humor and physical health was also examined by exploring how laughter can affect blood pressure on a person. High blood pressure can serve as a predictor of additional health issues, and have many contrary consequences on individual's health; such as high blood pressure raises the likelihood of stroke, heart attack, and renal failure and other potentially fatal situations of the patient (Guyton & Hall, 2005). If humor can lower blood pressure, it may serve as a useful way to improve health. Research also indicates that laughter itself may help reduce blood pressure. Some evidence supports the idea that blood pressure is related with humor.

Mindfulness can be trained, especially through the meditation practice. Frequent meditation practice is thought to improve self-regulating skills (Lutz, et al., 2008). A non-judgmental and acceptable attitude is another important aspect of many meditations practice. Mindfulness is an innate human capacity, and, "we are all attentive to one degree, moment by moment," although there are strong individual differences between individuals to the extent that they are generally aware of the present moment (i.e., the attentiveness of the characteristics). Mindfulness can be trained, especially through the meditation practice. Frequent meditation practice is thought to improve self-regulating skills (Lutz, et al., 2008). While one can focus one object (for example, breathing), during meditation, but when "distractors" occur the meditator takes a non-judgmental view (for example, just remember that

there is a sound without judging it) to them and then returns attention to the object of meditation. Quality of life (QoL) is a multifaceted notion that combines the physical, social, emotional as well as cognitive functioning of an individual's subjective perceptions (Koot, 2001). According to the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL, 1996), quality of life refers to how people perceive their place in life, shaped by the culture norms and values they live in and connected with their goals, aspirations, values, and concerns. Base on this description, quality of life is composed of several areas with psychological, physical health, environmental concerns, and social relations.

The perception of quality of life is intended from the psychological, environmental, physical, and social aspects (WHOQOL, 1997). Psychological principles of quality and life satisfaction stress not only the importance of physical health but also the absence of weaknesses in successful day-to-day and social accomplishments. Individual quality of life valuation is dictated by the nature of disease, the procedure is applied, and at times by a lengthy process of diagnosis and therapy (Roditi & Robinson, 2011).

Quality of life reflects the overall well-being of individuals and communities, encompassing both positive and negative aspects of life. It examines life satisfaction, covering aspects such as physical health, family, education, work, finances, safety, freedom, faith, and the environment. Empirical evidence confirms the significant role of communal relations for physical well-being over a lifetime. Poor quality of the relationship is a risk factor for death, cardiac disease, reduced wound healing, and poor view of health (Robles et al., 2014). Much empirical evidence has relied on the identification of the processes that might describe this association, including health habits, mental processes, and biological mechanisms. Nevertheless, it is equally important to examine whether definite groups of people are more susceptible to the consequences of disappointment with the relationships.

Marital and, more commonly, relationship satisfaction has been related to various outcomes for both individuals and couples, such as mental health, physical strength, cure of both physical

strength and mental health-related conditions, work efficiency, separation rates, and overall satisfaction with life (Fincham & Beach 2010). The robust analytical association between satisfaction with the relationship and these vital outcomes in life has resulted in multiple researches in this research area. This massive number of studies covers several domains of interest such as gender alterations in satisfaction, the influencing role of relationship satisfaction on other life areas including parenting, the influencing role of social and environmental factors on relationship satisfaction, marital satisfaction courses, how relationship satisfaction can be assessed, and the many possible predictors of relationship satisfaction (Fincham & Beach, 2010).

Satisfaction with relationships is considered as practical support mechanisms. The difference between apparent and attained support is significant, as individuals can feel alone despite being surrounded by others (Hawley & Cacioppo 2010). The difference between perceived support is also imperative. Besides, apparent support is more steadily associated with various measures of morbidity and mortality measures (Hawley & Cacioppo, 2010). Most of the existing research on this subject focuses on the correlates and predictors of married couples' satisfaction. The subjective acuity of satisfaction is a significant sign of relation consistency and has concerns for the permanence of the relationships, as less gratified relationships are more expected to end. Mindfulness is empirically and theoretically associated with mental well-being and overall health. The present study focuses on determining mediating role of relationship satisfaction on the association between humor, mindfulness and quality of life in patients with cardiovascular diseases. This study proposed that relationship satisfaction act as mediator and will have positive effect on quality of life of with cardiovascular disease patients.

Research Design

A cross sectional, quantitative research design was used. Data from different participants was

obtained through the use of purposive sampling technique.

Sample

Sample was comprised of N=160 patients of cardiovascular diseases with age ranging between 35 to 65 years. Sample was selected from Armed Forces Institute of Cardiology & National Institute of Heart Diseases (AFIC & NIHD) Rawalpindi

Inclusion criteria

Both married male and female patients diagnosed with Myocardial Infarction, Heart Failure, PCI, Angina and Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting with an age ranging between 35-65 years old were involved in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Unmarried individuals diagnosed with cardiovascular diseases with an age below 35 were not included. Patients with other serious medical illness were also not included in this study

Instruments

Demographics

Demographic sheet was used to gather data about gender, age, education, monthly income etc. Before collection of data, informed consents were taken from the participants.

Humor Styles Questionnaire (Martin, 2003)

The Humor Styles Questionnaire (HSQ) developed by Martin (2003), was employed to measure both positive and negative humor styles. This 32-item measure is divided into four subscales, two reflecting positive styles and two representing negative styles. The positive dimensions include Affiliative humor (e.g., “I don’t have to work very hard in making people laugh—I seem to be a naturally humorous person.”) and Self-enhancing humor (e.g., “I don’t need to be with other people to feel amused, I can usually find things to laugh about even when I’m by myself.”). The negative dimensions consist of Aggressive humor (e.g., “When telling jokes or saying funny things, I am usually not very concerned about how other people are taking it.”)

and Self-defeating humor (e.g., “I let people laugh at me or make fun at my expense more than I should.”). Participants rated their responses on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Reliability analysis yielded Cronbach’s alpha values of .77 for affiliative humor, .73 for self-enhancing humor, .58 for aggressive humor, and .83 for self-defeating humor.

Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale (Brown et al., 2003)

The Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) is a 15-item instrument developed by Brown et al. (2003), was used to measure a key aspect of mindfulness: a receptive mental state in which present-moment experiences are observed with attentive and sensitive awareness. The scale determines strong internal consistency, with Cronbach’s alpha values range between .80 and .90. It has also shown high test–retest reliability, as well as evidence of convergent, criterion, and known-groups validity. Findings from correlational, quasi-experimental, and experimental research indicate that the MAAS captures a distinct quality of consciousness that is associated with, and predictive of, various outcomes related to emotional regulation, behavior, interpersonal functioning, and overall well-being.

The World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire

The World Health Organization Quality of Life-Brief (WHOQOL-BREF) is a 26-item instrument developed as a abbreviated form of the WHOQOL-100. It assesses individuals’ perceived quality of life across four areas: Physical (“To what extent does physical pain prevent you from doing what you need to do?”), Psychological (“How much do you enjoy life?”), Social (“How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?”), and Environmental (“How safe do you feel in your daily life?”). Evidence indicates acceptable internal consistency for the Psychological, Physical and Environmental domains ($\alpha = .80-.82$), while the social domain demonstrates slightly lower reliability ($\alpha \approx .68$; Skevington et al., 2004).

Responses are rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with lower scores reflecting poorer quality of life and higher scores representing better quality of life

Couples Satisfaction Index (Funk & Rogge, 2007)

The Couples Satisfaction Index (CSI) is a 16-item designed to measure relationship satisfaction. Respondents reply to items such as, “In general, how often do you think that things between you and your partner are going well?!” on a 7-point scale. CSI scores are highly correlated to other relevant satisfaction measures (including all measures that originally contributed to their development) and differentiate between depressed and unstressed relationships (Funk & Rogge, 2007). The measure has an alpha of .98.

Procedure

Permission to use the required assessment tools in the study was taken from scales authors. Official permission was taken from the research and the development cell (R& D cell) Armed Forces

Institute of Cardiology (AFIC & NIHD) to get the information from the cardiac patients. Cardiac patients after fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria were recruited in the study. Informed consent was collected from the participants. Demographic sheet was used to gather data about participants’ gender, age and education etc.

Humor Styles Questionnaire (Martin, 2003) and Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale (Brown & Ryan 2003) was used to measure levels of humor and mindfulness among patients with cardiovascular diseases. The World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire (WHOQOL Group, 1997) and Couples Satisfaction Index (Funk & Rogge, 2007) was adopted to measure quality of life and level of relationship satisfaction among cardiovascular diseases patients respectively. Statistical package, SPSS version 23 was used for data entry and analysis. The descriptive statistics was applied to categorize the study population. The frequency tables are constructed and presented in percentages.

Results

Table 1

Frequency table for Demographic Variables(N=160)

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Male	83	51.9
Female	77	48.1
Age		
35-45	46	28.7
46-55	66	41.3
56-65	48	30.0
Education		
Uneducated	20	12.5
Middle	32	20.0
Matric	38	23.8
Intermediate	48	30.0
Graduate	18	11.3
Postgraduate	4	2.5
Occupation		
Govt job	64	40.0
Private job	22	13.8

None	74	46.3
Monthly Income		
High > lac	19	11.7
Medium (50,000-1 lac)	81	49.7
Low (< 50,000)	60	36.8
Family System		
Joint	98	61.3
Nuclear	61	38.1
Separate	1	.6
Residential Area		
Urban	105	65.6
Rural	54	33.8
Diabetes		
Yes	42	26.3
No	118	73.8
Hypertension		
Yes	60	37.5
No	100	62.5
Family History of Cardiac Disease		
Yes	58	36.7
No	102	63.7
Family History of Mental Illness		
Yes	11	6.9
No	149	93.1

Note: f=Frequency %= Percentage

Table 1 demonstrates the demographic characteristics of patients with cardiovascular diseases. Demographic characteristics were computed in relation to frequency (f) and percentage.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables (N=160)

Variables	K	a	M	SD	Range		Skew	Kurtosis
					Potential	Actual		
HSQ	32	.76	103.2	19.8	32-224	157-157	-.21	-.50
AH	8	.79	5.4	10.0	8-56	16-56	-.82	-.23
SHE	8	.76	3.1	8.9	8-56	7-40	.01	-.85
AGH	8	.62	2.8	6.9	8-56	9-44	1.2	1.2
SDH	8	.69	1.9	6.9	8-56	8-40	1.1	1.2
MAAS	15	.80	70.6	11.8	16-90	39-90	-.572	-.430
WHOQOL	26	.88	10.9	10.9	26-130	59-125	-.523	1.52
CSI	16	.92	8.97	.92	0-80	40-81	-.479	-.369

Note: HSQ= Humor Styles Questionnaire; AH= Affiliative Humor; SHE= Self-Enhancing Humor; AGH= Aggressive Humor, SDH= Self-defeating Humor MAAS= Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale; CSI= Couple Satisfaction Index; WHOQOL= World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire. **p <.01. *p <.05

Table 2 indicates the mean, standard deviation, range, skewness, kurtosis and Cronbach alpha reliability of study variables. These descriptive statistics were calculated to examine the overall data distribution for the study variables. Results displays that data is normally distributed. The skewness and kurtosis values mostly ranged between -1 to +1 and they are statistically standard. All of the scales are having good alpha reliability. HSQ (Humor Styles Questionnaire) has .76

reliability, Affiliative Humor Style has .79 reliability, Self-Enhancing Humor Style has .76 reliability, Aggressive Humor Style has .62 reliability, Self-defeating Humor Style has .69 reliability, MAAS (Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale) has .80 reliability, WHOQOL (World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire) has .88 reliability and CSI (Couple Satisfaction Index) has .92 reliability.

Table 3
Correlation Matrix of Study Variables (N=160)

Sr No.	Var	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	HSQ	-	.308**	.868**	.558**	.641**	-.192	.303**
2	AH	-		.075	.389**	.385**	.318**	.225**
3	SHE	-			.445**	.545**	-.116	.271**
4	AGH	-				.688**	.507**	.062
5	SDH	-					-.414**	.082
6	MAAS	-						.232**
7	WHOQOL	-						

Note: HSQ= Humor Styles Questionnaire; AH= Affiliative Humor; SHE= Self Enhancing Humor; AGH= Aggressive Humor, SDH= Self-defeating Humor MAAS= Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale; CSI= Couple Satisfaction Index; WHOQOL= World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire. **p <.01. ***p <.001.

Table no.3 indicates that there is significant positive relationship between humor styles with its subscale (affiliative, self-enhancing, self-defeating and aggressive humor) and quality of life. Table

also shows significant positive relationship between mindfulness and quality of life in patients with cardiovascular diseases.

Table 4
Linear Regression showing Quality of Life Predicted by Humor and Mindfulness among Patients with Cardiovascular Disease (N=160)

	β	S.E	95%CI	
			LL	UL
Constant	53.4	7.04	40.8	68.9
HSQ	.279	.068	.11	.29
MASS	.201	.041	.15	.42
R ²	.179			
F	17.1			
Δ R	.169			

Note: HSQ= Humor Styles Questionnaire; m=MAAS= Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale; CSI= Couple Satisfaction Index; WHOQOL= World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire; R^2 = R Square; ΔR^2 = R Square Change; B= Unstandardized Regression Coefficient; CI= Confidence Interval; LL= Lower Limit; UL= Upper Limit. **p <.01. *p <.05

Table 4 indicates that humor styles and mindfulness have significant positive impact on quality of life in patients having cardiovascular disease (P=.000)

Table 5
Mediating Role of Relationship Satisfaction between Humor Styles, and Quality of Life among Patients with Cardiovascular Disease (N=160)

Variable	Quality of Life												
	Total Effect				Direct Effect				Indirect Effect		95%CI		
	β	S.E	t	p	β	S.E	t	p	β	S.E	p	LL	UL
Humor	.17	.042	4.00	.0001	.102	.040	2.54	.011	.066	.020	.0001	45.5	59.8

Note: B= co-efficient, CI= Confidence Interval, LL= Lower Limit, UL= Upper Limit of 95% bias-corrected, *p <.05; ***p <.001.

Table 5 shows the results of mediation analysis were significant. p value is greater than .005 which means relationship satisfactions mediates the relationship between humor and quality of life.

The results revealed that relationship satisfaction have relationship with quality of life and humor in cardiovascular diseases patients.

Table 6
Mediating Role of Relationship Satisfaction between Humor Styles, and Quality of Life among Patients with Cardiovascular Disease (N=160)

Variable	Quality of Life												
	Total Effect				Direct Effect				Indirect Effect		95%CI		
	β	S.E	t	p	β	S.E	t	p	β	S.E	p	LL	UL
MAAS	.214	.071	2.9	.003	.072	.06	1.0	.3008	.142	.04	.003	.07	.35

Note: B= co-efficient, CI= Confidence Interval, LL= Lower Limit, UL= Upper Limit of 95% bias-corrected, *p <.05; ***p <.001.

Table 6 shows the results of mediation analysis were significant. p value is greater than .005 which means relationship satisfactions serve as a mediator between mindfulness and quality of life. Results revealed that relationship satisfaction have relationship with quality of life and mindfulness among cardiovascular diseases patients

Discussion

The central focus of the current research was to determine the influence of humor styles and mindfulness on the life quality among cardiovascular disease patients and finding out the relationship satisfaction as a mediator. The sample comprised of 160 patients with cardiovascular diseases from Armed Forces Institute of Cardiology Rawalpindi.

Humor and mindfulness appear effective in reducing the stress experienced due to cardiovascular diseases. It was hypothesized that positive humor styles (self-improving and affiliative humor) will positively affect the quality of life whereas negative humor (aggressive and self-destructive) will negatively affect the quality of life of patients with cardiovascular diseases. The findings from these analyses confirm the hypothesis that the practice of positive humor can act as an efficacious coping mechanism for enhancing the patient's life quality. Finding through Pearson product correlation indicated that affiliative and self-enhancing humor styles had significant positive relationship with quality of life in patients with cardiovascular disease. While self-defeating and aggressive humor style had non-significant positive relationship with quality of life among patients having cardiovascular disease. This suggest that patients with good sense of humor will have good quality of life. Both positive and negative humor styles are positively related with quality of life in patients having cardiovascular diseases.

Second hypothesis was that mindfulness will act as a positive indicator of quality of life among patients having cardiovascular diseases. Finding through Pearson product correlation indicated significant positive correlation between mindfulness and quality of life in patients with cardiovascular diseases. Analysis of data revealed

that findings are consistent with the literature review which revealed numerous studies linking mindfulness and quality of life. The state of mindfulness also contributes to a sense of psychological wellbeing and equilibrium (Carmody & Baer, 2008). Brown and Ryan (2003) studied in correlational research that mindfulness has association with lower levels of depression, aggression and self-consciousness in addition to increased positive effect and life satisfaction. Keng's (2011) found in his study that mindfulness is positively associated with a number of mental health metrics like higher levels of positive effect, life satisfaction, control of emotions, and lower levels of negative effect and psychopathological symptoms.

Next hypothesis stated that humor and mindfulness will positively predict quality of life among patients in cardiovascular disease. Finding through linear regression showed that humor styles had significant positive impact on quality of life in patients having cardiovascular disease. The humorous approach to everyday life may establish positive cognitive (perspective of the world), mental, and physiological state changes (Lockwood, 1991). It was found that humor help the individuals with different types of cancer, mental health issues, depression, and consolation for those who die. Humor was listed as one of the healthiest ways to cope with; which make those who use them psychologically and physically healthier. Research on coping humor has focused mainly on populations with special needs and clinical populations, since coping humor was considered as a technique to manage the unavoidable stresses of aging or being chronically ill.

Studies show that mindfulness has been related with a higher degree of life satisfaction (Brown & Rayan, 2003) The state of mindfulness also results in a sense of balance and mental contentment (Carmody & Baer, 2008). Short-term mindfulness meditation training in the medical field has been found effective in the treatment of long-lasting pain (Miller et al., 1995) and decreasing response to stress and enhancing the immune system, thus lowers the chances of potential disease (Davidson et al., 2003).

Next hypothesis was that relationship satisfaction would mediate the correlation between humor and quality of life in patients having cardiovascular diseases. The results showed that humor styles and quality of life was mediated by relationship satisfaction among patient with cardiovascular diseases. In research by Goldsmith, 2004, relationship satisfaction mediated the impact of humor functions on both psychological and social health. This result proves the health implications of the social support management. Past studies found that the relationship satisfaction of patients with cardiovascular diseases showed positive correlation with humor and quality of life. Bippus et al., (2011) suggested that use of humor during disputes had disparate effects on speakers and listeners. The more humor people used themselves in conflict, the more they were happy with their relationships and the less they felt the conflict had increased. Moreover, patients with broader social networks and enhanced emotional well-being are well equipped to manage illnesses (Lefcourt, 2001). Therefore, it is clear that partnerships support the physiological, psychological, and social wellbeing of an individual.

Implications

The outcomes of this research have several significant implications for people suffering from cardiac diseases, caretakers, health care professionals and staff in hospitals. It can help in creating stress management services where perceived stress can be minimized by encouraging patients to use humor coping techniques and mindfulness along with increasing the social support structure and healthy dietary habits, thereby strengthening interpersonal relationships at the same time. Happy and optimistic patients have more tolerance and coping skills in handling stress along with a strong immune system. Hence training to use humor and mindfulness will restructure many of the negative attitudes and health-related habits of the CVD patient. It is possible to generate awareness campaigns and counseling sessions by demonstrating how these stressors related to health risks can be minimized by both raising knowledge and improving good

coping skills (such as humor and mindfulness) and turning people's attention to more positive elements in their lives. With this awareness, social work professionals will work on recovery plans and try to improve stress management services among Pakistan's increasing number of cardiac patients.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

The present study has a number of limitations. Firstly, results cannot be extended beyond this sample, the sample size can also be taken on a much larger scale to generalize and eliminate variations and biases from individuals. Secondly, the data was gathered from a single hospital. Samples from some other hospitals in Pakistan could be recruited. Thirdly, more researches could be done to explore how humor can be a good coping technique in handling daily situations rather than coping with health-related stress.

Conclusion

Humor, mindfulness and relationship satisfaction may enhance the positive psychological functioning and restructure CVD patient's negative attitudes and behaviors related to health. The finding from this study revealed that humor styles and mindfulness had positive impact on quality of life in patients having cardiovascular disease. Humor styles, mindfulness and quality of life was mediated by relationship satisfaction among patients with cardiovascular disease. People with higher levels of positivity, hope, and happiness, strengthened through a positive sense of humor, are expected to perceive their lives as less stressful, and hence report more optimistic levels of both physical and psychological health.

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